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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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On That One Day

Outside the rain was pouring
Blurring tiny rays of eastern skies;
Drenching the fallen leaves and drowning
With rotten twigs hovered by hungry skies.

Outside the rain was shattering
Every fragile petal from a bloom.
It swayed and swung till morning
Worn out and drained to doom.

The leaves and twigs and petals
Are helpless so they say.
So as the men with hearts of metals
Are doomed to end one day.

And when that one day comes
We've got to grab the chance.
To humbly face Our maker
On bended knees and white-washed hands.